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E3.6.2: Final design for distributed AI operations in 6G v1.0

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4 List of Acronyms

CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
DevOps	Development and Operations
DoF	Degree of Freedom
E2AP	E2 Application Protocol
E2SM	E2 Service Model
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLaaS	ML as a Service
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RIC	Radio Intelligent Controller
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SoA	State-of-the-Art
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
XAI	eXplainable AI

5 Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the works carried out in Task A3.1. It reviews the state-of-the-art in MLOps for network automation, covering research and standardization efforts, identifying gaps, and proposing a future-proof architecture for 6G networks. It starts by examining current research activities and standardization initiatives, highlighting their impact on MLOps technologies. A gaps analysis identifies key areas needing further development. The proposed final distributed MLOps architecture for 6G emphasizes trustworthiness and compliance with ETSI ZSM and O-RAN slicing standards, detailing its lifecycle and benefits. Additionally, the document discusses a Kubeflow-based MLOps architecture for cloud-edge environments, explaining why Kubeflow is chosen and how it integrates within the architecture. The document also describes the Kubeflow-based implementation of the MLOps pipeline.

6 Introduction

In nowadays rapidly evolving telecommunications landscape, the native integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) into network operations is needed. Much like the separation between the user plane (UP) and control plane (CP), a modular and scalable integration of AI/ML as a native component into the future-proof 6G architecture necessitates consolidating all MLOps into a dedicated plane. This plane can be designed as a distributed cross-domain slice, managing the lifecycle of AI models, and delivering them as artifacts tailored to the target technological domain of a network slice. This approach promotes model reusability, reduces training workloads, and, consequently, reduces the carbon footprint. This innovative 6GENABLERS-AI distributed architecture was aptly termed "SliceOps." in E3.3.2. The current deliverable E3.6.2, presents its final version, highlighting the interconnection with OPTARE telemetry platform and OpenNebula orchestration in a cloud-edge continuum. Specifically, the architecture includes Monitoring and Feature Store which is a critical step in ML practices, supporting data preparation and model design by feeding the MLOps pipeline with vast amounts of online/offline data, including resources and application metrics. OPTARE integrates FEAST to manage data features for offline training and online inference, ensuring model consistency and data visibility. I2CAT Statistical Data Aggregation preprocesses data and computes the empirical cumulative distribution function (E-CDF) of predicted CPU usage to minimize the probability of CPU falling below a target threshold. Model Training, Confidence Evaluation, and Saving involve continuous model training using offline FEAST data, employing explanation-based confidence metrics to assess and ensure model robustness. Retraining is triggered by feedback loops if model confidence deteriorates, with successful models stored in the registry for future production. Finally, the model is served to OpenNebula AIOps module that interacts with the edge orchestrator. A Kubeflow implementation of this MLOps architecture is finally presented.

7 MLOps for Network Automation: State-of-the-Art Review

This section reviews the recent endeavours to integrate MLOps into wireless networks, as an enabler of AI-driven automation. It starts with research efforts and then delves into standardisation aspects. Finally, a gap analysis is presented.

7.1 Research and Standardization Relevant to MLOps

7.1.1 Research

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in intelligent resource orchestration and the need for MLOps and eXplainable AI (XAI) in various domains. Indeed, Samaras et al. introduced an MLOps automation platform for optimised network slice Life-cycle Management (LCM) using a cloud-native approach¹. Their event-based framework enables zero-touch MLOps, automatically adapting and optimising the system based on the accuracy performance of the training job. This approach ensures efficient and streamlined management of network slices throughout their life cycle.

Similarly, Zaidi et al. proposed an ML as a Service (MLaaS) approach for 5G IoT, employing an MLOps framework known as TMLaaS architecture². This framework facilitates the unification of ML systems for seamless implementation, deployment, and maintenance operations. By incorporating MLOps principles, the authors address the complexities associated with managing ML models in the context of 5G and IoT.

In another study, Li et al. proposed an MLOps life cycle based on Reinforcement Learning (RL) to automate and reproduce the model development process in open radio access network (O-RAN) deployment³. The authors introduced principles and practices for developing data-derived optimal decision-making strategies. By leveraging MLOps, the RL model development process becomes automated and reproducible, facilitating efficient O-RAN deployment.

¹ G. Samaras, V. Theodorou, D. Laskaratos, N. Psaromanolakis, M. Mertiri, and A. Valantasis, "QMP: A Cloud-native MLOps Automation Platform for Zero-Touch Service Assurance in 5G Systems," in Proc. IEEE Int. Mediterranean Conf. on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), Sep. 2022.

² S. A. R. Zaidi, A. M. Hayajneh, M. Hafeez, and Q. Z. Ahmed, "Unlocking Edge Intelligence Through Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML)," IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 100 867–100 877, Sep. 2022.

³ P. Li et al., "RLOps: Development Life-Cycle of Reinforcement Learning Aided Open RAN," IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 113 808–113 826, Oct. 2022.

Besides, Tsourdinis et al. developed a service-aware dynamic slice allocation scheme using an MLOps-based distributed ML architecture⁴, which enables dynamic and efficient resource utilisation.

On the other hand, the challenges of developing XAI methods and demonstrating how causal inference plays a role in 6G technology has been highlighted⁵. Similarly, in⁶, the significance of explainability in 5G is highlighted for essential services and device-to-device architectural security. Additionally, the importance of causal inference in 6G technology is emphasised.

Researchers in⁷ also acknowledge the importance of explainability in upcoming 6G networks, especially regarding its applications in resolving handover and resource allocation issues. In a comparative study⁸ of XAI techniques, SHAP is suggested as the most effective method for identifying the cause of service level agreement (SLA) violations. However, these studies focus on *post-hoc* explainability and lack the use of quantitative metrics to evaluate the fidelity of explanations and consider it during the training process in an *in-hoc* fashion, which is required to generate trustworthy models from the origin.

7.1.2 Standardisation

Alongside research contributions, some organisations' initiatives are relevant for MLOps components in telecommunications. The European telecommunications standards institute experiential networked intelligence (ETSI ENI) is defining a cognitive network management architecture leveraging AI techniques. The architecture aims to provide fully automated service provision, operation, and assurance.

The corresponding closed-loop AI mechanisms can be leveraged in the MLOps lifecycle. Unlike ETSI ENI, which focuses on AI techniques, European telecommunication standards institute zero-touch service management (ETSI ZSM)⁹ is investigating automation challenges faced by operators and vertical industries. The group works on end-to-end (E2E) architecture and services automation to solve radical changes in the way networks are managed and orchestrated in the pivotal deployment of 5G and

⁴ T. Tsourdinis, I. Chatzistefanidis, N. Makris, and T. Korakis, "AI-driven Service-aware Real-time Slicing for beyond 5G Networks," in Proc. IEEE INFOCOM 2022 - IEEE Conf. on Computer Communications Workshops, May. 2022.

⁵ Y. Xiao, G. Shi, and M. Krutz, "Towards ubiquitous AI in 6G with federated learning," ArXiv, vol. abs/2004.13563, 2020.

⁶ P. Muñoz, I. de la Bandera, E. J. Khatib, A. Gómez-Andrades, I. Serrano, and R. Barco, "Root cause analysis based on temporal analysis of metrics toward self-organizing 5G networks," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 2811–2824, 2017.

⁷ C. Li, W. Guo, S. C. Sun, S. Al-Rubaye, and A. Tsourdos, "Trustworthy deep learning in 6G-enabled mass autonomy: From concept to quality-of-trust key performance indicators," IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 112–121, 2020.

⁸ A. Terra, R. Inam, S. Baskaran, P. Batista, I. Burdick, and E. Fersman, "Explainability methods for identifying Root-cause of SLA violation prediction in 5G network," in GLOBECOM 2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference, 2020, pp. 1–7.

⁹ ETSI ZSM 009-1, Zero-touch network and service management (zsm); closed loop automation; enablers. V0.10.5, (2021-01).

network slicing. In this intent, an MLOps approach with lifecycle management of ML models for reproducible ML pipelines would be necessary.

7.2 Gaps Analysis of MLOps for Networks

The stakeholders in the network slicing ecosystem need innovations to natively embed MLOps into the network architecture while enhancing the interpretability of the black-box AI decision-making process to attain human trust. In this regard, the main gaps in MLOps for networking can be summarised as follows:

- **Transparent AI:** this assumes the incorporation of explainability into the MLOps pipeline, where XAI metrics can be included as a hyperparameter or observation to trigger the re-training of AI models and control their transparency. In this respect, several metrics exist such as *confidence*, *log-odd*, and *comprehensiveness*¹⁰.
- **Cost-effective workload:** where the concept of transfer learning and model reusability are necessary to avoid re-training when it comes to similar tasks. This similarity can be characterised by a statistical distance such as the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the weights of models after the first training. This would allow a dramatic reduction in training cost.
- **Monitoring data:** MLOps needs robust solutions for data lineage, tracking, and monitoring. Improving monitoring data for MLOps involves standardising data formats like JSON for ease of analysis, collecting high-granularity metrics and logs, enabling real-time streaming (e.g., via Kafka or HTTP), implementing distributed tracing using tools like Jaeger or Zipkin to capture end-to-end interactions, and including contextual metadata (e.g., model version, hyperparameters) for effective issue diagnosis.
- **Hyperparameters tracking:** numerous MLOps tools are actively addressing the challenge of tracking hyperparameters, dependencies, and code versions effectively. Tools like MLflow, Kubeflow, and DVC (Data Version Control) offer solutions to monitor and manage hyperparameters alongside code and data versions, ensuring reproducibility and transparency in machine learning experiments. These platforms streamline the tracking of essential elements, aiding in model development and lifecycle management within the rapidly evolving field of machine learning operations.

¹⁰ B. Brik, H. Chergui, L. Zanzi, F. Devoti, A. Ksentini, M.S. Siddiqui, X. Costa-Perez, and C. Verikoukis, (2023). A Survey on Explainable AI for 6G O-RAN: Architecture, Use Cases, Challenges and Research Directions. ArXiv, abs/2307.00319.

8 Final Distributed MLOps Architecture for Future-Proof 6G Networks

8.1 Trustworthy MLOps Architecture for 6G

Just as there is a separation between the user plane (UP) and control plane (CP), integrating AI/ML as an integral component into the future 6G architecture in a modular and scalable manner necessitates consolidating all MLOps into a dedicated plane. This plane could be practically designed as a distributed cross-domain slice, managing the life cycle of AI models and delivering them as tailored artefacts for the target technological domain. This approach promotes model reusability for similar tasks, decreases training workload, and consequently reduces carbon footprint. This architecture, known as SliceOps¹¹, characterises the 6GENABLERS-AI framework.

8.1.1 Final Distributed MLOps Lifecycle

The SliceOps foundation relies on a practice aiming to standardise production methods through incorporating the concept of CI and CD, producing thereby reliable software and AI solutions in short cycles. In 6G AI-native networks, SliceOps modular design allows the evolution, upgrade, and scaling of the MLOps layer and its AI functions separately from the service layers.¹²

Figure 1 shows the pictorial representation of an operationalizing AI-native slice (Kubernetes namespace). The i2CAT MLOps provides predictive AI services to the OpenNebula Edge orchestrator, to guide its OneFlow scaling policies. The MLOps pipeline also triggers retraining upon the reception of new data from OPTARE's feature store, FEAST, to meet the target model's confidence. The pipeline is described in the sequel.

¹¹ F. Rezaadeh, H. Chergui, L. Alonso and C. Verikoukis, "SliceOps: Explainable MLOps for Streamlined Automation-Native 6G Networks," in *IEEE Wireless Communications*, doi: 10.1109/MWC.007.2300144. [Online] Available: ArXiv, abs/2307.01658.

¹² M. Asad *et al.*, "6GENABLERS: A Holistic Approach to Establish Pervasive Trust in 6G Networks," *2023 IEEE 28th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)*, Edinburgh, United Kingdom, 2023, pp. 55-60, doi: 10.1109/CAMAD59638.2023.10478383.

Figure 1 Final Distributed MLOps workflow including monitoring, re-training, confidence check and deploying ML model as a service on the orchestrator

- Monitoring and Feature Store:** It is considered as a backbone step in ML practices where data acquisition is utilised for data preparation and model design processes. It feeds the MLOps pipeline with online/offline data encompassing e.g., available resources and holoportation application metrics. This component can store structured and unstructured data on a very large scale. Specifically, OPTARE integrates FEAST (Feature Store) to facilitate efficient management of data features, crucial for both offline training and online inference. This integration ensures consistency in model behaviour across different operational stages and enhances data visibility and access during critical decision-making processes.
- Statistical Data Aggregation:** This component is responsible for data preprocessing and statistical aggregation. Specifically, the empirical cumulative distribution function (E-CDF) of the predicted CPU is computed over a time window and included in the NeSy loss function to minimise the probability of CPU lower than a target threshold. The E-CDF is often employed in data analysis and non-parametric statistics. Given data with observations (x_1, \dots, x_n) , the E-CDF at a specific value γ is calculated as the proportion of data points greater than or equal to γ . In mathematical terms it is defined as,

$$F_{E-CDF} = \frac{\text{Number of observations} < \gamma}{\text{Total number of observations}}$$

This function provides a step-wise representation of the cumulative probability distribution of the data, allowing for a visual understanding of the data's spread and characteristics.

- Model Training, Confidence Evaluation and Saving:** It consists of a set of processes for the execution of continuous model training automatically with offline FEAST data. The ML model training runs a local optimization task, while the model explanation involves an *explainer*, either attribution-based (e.g., Integrated Gradient, Saliency Maps) or perturbation-based (e.g., SHAP¹³). To characterise the trustworthiness of the prediction model, we invoke the explanation-based confidence metric¹⁴. As depicted in Figure 2, its rationale lies in the fact that slightly shifting the value of high magnitude features (in the sense of attributions) is an acceptable way to determine the model's conformance. In essence, the explanation (feature attributions) informs the process of assessing confidence. When a model's explanation highlights certain features as highly influential, the confidence in the model's predictions can be gauged by examining how robust those predictions are when these significant features are altered in the input neighbourhood. Therefore, the explanation (attributions) directly guides the method for evaluating and understanding the model's confidence in its predictions. In our context, such an approach is vital because there will likely be no change in the SLA group (SLA violation or non-violation) if we sample over low attribution features space. Upon the evaluation the NeSy prediction, the model retraining is triggered using a feedback loop whenever there is a deterioration in the model confidence following new training data arrival (new unexplored samples). Finally, in case the model fulfils the target performance, it will be registered and stored in the model registry to be promoted into production later.

Figure 2 Feature masking for model confidence evaluation

¹³ S. M. Lundberg and S. Lee, "A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions," in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30, 2017.

¹⁴ S. Jha, S. Raj, S. Fernandes, S. K. Jha, S. Jha, B. Jalaian, G. Verma, and A. Swami, "Attribution-based confidence metric for deep neural networks," in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, vol. 32. Curran Associates, Inc., 2019.

- **Model Serving and Deployment:** The next step after training and evaluation is to retrieve the registered model for encapsulation and move to the production stage in the form of a model prediction service. The trained model is continuously exposed and delivered to the Orchestrator AIOps module.

8.1.2 ETSI ZSM Compliance

The design of SliceOps solution closely adheres to the ZSM framework. The standardization process for ETSI ZSM is still in its early stages, with preliminary specifications based on a high level of abstraction. The core concept of the closed-loop AI system is to utilize context-aware and metadata-driven policies to allow for efficient and fast identification as well as incorporate new conditions while updating knowledge and making robust and actionable decisions. As shown in Figure 1, SliceOps is a practice toward deploying a more realistic closed-loop scheme to fulfill viable automation solutions for network slicing control. SliceOps manages the lifecycle of AI models in a closed-loop way that includes model performance monitoring, re-training, and delivery. It extends the ZSM framework to manage, besides the service functions, the underlying AI functions, which are natively supported in a standalone slice.

8.1.3 O-RAN Slicing Compliance

The SliceOps framework can be adapted to use case 3 of O-RAN slicing, which is related to resource allocation optimization, requirements, and architecture¹⁵. Specifically, SliceOps layer can be developed as rApps at the non-real-time (non-RT) radio intelligent controller (RIC). Thanks to its architecture that brings valuable differentiators by leveraging XAI and CI/CD, SliceOps would implement new use cases with agility and automate network operations. In this respect, rApps need to access abundant monitoring data---such as traffic load, latency, and signal strength---through the O1 interface to efficiently carry out their designated functions in time-demanding training procedures. Then, the model or policy trained by SliceOps can be packaged as an artifact and delivered via the A1 interface to run on the Near-RT RIC interface as xApp. This model deployment is performed using REST APIs over HTTP for the transfer of such JSON objects. For dynamic network optimization purposes, this xApp would control the underlying O-RAN components, namely, the central unit-control plane (O-CU-CP), different slice open central unit-user plane (O-CU-UP), and open distributed unit plane (O-DU) by using the E2 interface. The E2 interface encompasses two protocols, namely the E2 application protocol (E2AP) and the E2 service model (E2SM).

¹⁵ O-RAN.WG1, "Slicing Architecture Technical Specification 9.0," in ORAN Specifications, March 2023.

8.2 Benefits of the Architecture

The advantages of defining an AI plane in the architecture can be summarized as follows:

- **Scalability/Evolution:**
 - Efficient Resource Allocation: Separating the AI plane allows for dedicated resources for AI-related tasks, such as model inference and data processing. This improves the scalability of AI workloads, enabling the allocation of additional computing resources as needed for growing data volumes and computational demands.
 - Easier Upgrades: The AI plane's isolation makes it easier to evolve and update AI models, algorithms, and processing pipelines without disrupting other system components. This agility supports the rapid integration of new AI technologies and improvements.
- **Modularity:**
 - Clear Role Separation: Defining an AI plane provides a clear separation of responsibilities between AI-related tasks and other system functions. This modular architecture simplifies system design and maintenance, making it easier to manage and troubleshoot AI components independently.
 - Customization and Interchangeability: Modularity in the AI plane allows for the customization and interchangeability of AI models and algorithms. Teams can experiment with different AI approaches and integrate them seamlessly into the system.
- **Reusability:**
 - Reusable AI Components: A well-defined AI plane encourages the development of reusable AI components, such as pre-trained models, data preprocessing modules, and feature extraction pipelines. These components can be shared across multiple projects and applications, promoting efficiency and consistency.
 - Interoperability: Reusable AI components within the AI plane can be integrated into various applications and services, enhancing interoperability and reducing the need to reinvent AI solutions for each use case.

9 Kubeflow-Based MLOps Architecture

This section provides background information regarding available tools to support MLOps which will be investigated in this project as potential solutions for implementing the proposed architecture. Please, note that this section does not aim to cover all available tools but rather to present an overview of the different tools available, with a focus on those that are open source. To this end, we have structured this section into

9.1 Why Kubeflow?

Regarding End-to-end MLOps platforms, there is a diverse array of open-source platforms available, including Kubeflow.

*Kubeflow*¹⁶ can be used for data preprocessing, model training, model optimization, prediction serving, and monitoring in production environments. It simplifies the deployment of ML models on Kubernetes. The workloads can be deployed locally, on-premise, or in cloud environments¹⁷. Figure 3 provides an overview of the Kubeflow platform components.

Figure 3 Kubeflow model architecture¹⁶

Table 1 summarizes the main tasks in the MLOps lifecycle supported by these frameworks. From this table, we can appreciate that despite the availability of several MLOps platforms, many of them have limitations regarding mainly tasks related to data processing (DP) and operation and monitoring (OM) phases. Additionally, not all these tools can be seamlessly integrated, potentially leading to compatibility issues. Therefore,

¹⁶ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

¹⁷ G. Recupito et al., "A Multivocal Literature Review of MLOps Tools and Features," 2022 48th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), Gran Canaria, Spain, 2022, pp. 84-91, doi: 10.1109/SEAA56994.2022.00021.

there is still work to be done in developing user-friendly and fully automated MLOps platforms.

Table 1 MLOps platforms supported capabilities in the MLOps phases .

Phase	Data Preprocessing (DP)						Model Training (MT)					Model Deployment (MD)			Operations and Monitoring (OM)		
Platform	DP-1	DP-2	DP-3	DP-4	DP-5	DP-6	MT-1	MT-2	MT-3	MT-4	MT-5	MD-1	MD-2	MD-3	OM-1	OM-2	OM-3
Kubeflow (v1.3.0)		x			x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		
MLFlow (v1.14.1)									x	x		x	x	x			
Polyaxon (v1.9.5)					x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
TFX (v0.30.0)		x	x	x	x				x			x	x	x		x	x

DP-1: Data Source Handling

DP-2: Data Preprocessing and Transformations

DP-3: Data Quality Measurement Support through Metrics

DP-4: Data Management

DP-5: Data Versioning

DP-6: Data Labeling

MT-1: Model Type Selection

MT-2: Hyperparameter Tuning

MT-3: Tracking

MT-4: Integration Friendly

MT-5: Code Versioning

MD-1: Model Packaging

MD-2: Model Registry

MD-3: Support for Different Deployment Patterns

OM-1: System Monitoring

OM-2: Input Data Monitoring

OM-3: Model's Performance Monitoring

9.2 Kubeflow-Based MLOps Architecture in Cloud-Edge

Kubeflow offers several advantages, such as scalability, portability, reproducibility, and integration. By leveraging Kubernetes, it ensures that ML workflows can scale efficiently with the underlying infrastructure. Its portability allows workflows to be deployed on any Kubernetes-supported platform, whether on-premises, in the cloud, or in a hybrid environment. Features like pipeline versioning and metadata tracking enhance the reproducibility of ML experiments, while seamless integration with existing CI/CD systems promotes smooth incorporation into the overall software development lifecycle.

Kubeflow is suitable for various use cases, including end-to-end ML workflows, from data ingestion and preprocessing to training, tuning, and deployment. It is also beneficial for collaborative research, enabling data scientists and researchers to work together more effectively using shared resources and standardized workflows. Additionally, Kubeflow supports production-grade ML applications, allowing enterprises to deploy and manage these applications reliably and efficiently.

A significant component of Kubeflow is its Pipelines platform, which allows users to build and deploy portable, scalable ML workflows based on Docker containers. This platform offers a user-friendly interface for composing and managing ML workflows, enabling versioning, tracking, and reproducibility of experiments. In addition to Pipelines, Kubeflow supports various frameworks like TensorFlow, PyTorch, and MXNet for training ML models, offering distributed training capabilities that facilitate the training of large models across multiple nodes.

Each step in a pipeline is defined as a reusable component, which can be containerized. This modular approach promotes consistency and efficiency by allowing users to reuse components across different pipelines and projects. Once a pipeline is defined, it can be executed on a Kubernetes cluster, with Kubeflow Pipelines handling the orchestration of these steps. This ensures they are executed in the correct order and manages

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dependencies between steps. This orchestration capability is crucial for managing complex workflows that require precise coordination and resource management.

Using Kubeflow Pipelines involves several steps, from setting up your environment to defining and executing your machine learning workflows. The first step is to have an active Kubernetes cluster. This can be done by having a local deployment of Kubernetes using Minikube, or the respective Kubernetes versions using traditional cloud environments such as Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud Engine or Microsoft Azure (Among others). After the cluster has been established, it is now the turn to install Kubeflow Pipelines.

```
export PIPELINE_VERSION=2.1.0

kubectl apply -k "github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/manifests/kustomize/cluster-scoped-resources?ref=$PIPELINE_VERSION"

kubectl wait --for condition=established --timeout=60s crd/applications.app.k8s.io

kubectl apply -k "github.com/kubeflow/pipelines/manifests/kustomize/env/platform-agnostic-pns?ref=$PIPELINE_VERSION"

kubectl get po -A
```


NAMESPACE	NAME	READY	STATUS	RESTARTS	AGE
kube-system	coredns-7db6d8ff4d-4b6qd	1/1	Running	0	4h3m
kube-system	etcd-minikube	1/1	Running	0	4h4m
kube-system	kube-apiserver-minikube	1/1	Running	1 (3h49m ago)	4h4m
kube-system	kube-controller-manager-minikube	1/1	Running	0	4h4m
kube-system	kube-proxy-b9ttx	1/1	Running	0	4h3m
kube-system	kube-scheduler-minikube	1/1	Running	0	4h4m
kube-system	storage-provisioner	1/1	Running	2 (3h48m ago)	4h4m
kubeflow	cache-deployer-deployment-65fb47dd94-j7xm5	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	cache-server-657b5f8474-pwn4g	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	metadata-envoy-deployment-758c78ccb9-4kxtp	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	metadata-grpc-deployment-68d6f447cc-g5smw	1/1	Running	9 (3h38m ago)	3h59m
kubeflow	metadata-writer-6bf88bb8c4-mp78c	1/1	Running	3 (3h41m ago)	3h59m
kubeflow	mlnio-59b68688b5-xcbcq	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-6fd7df65fd-hph4h	1/1	Running	6 (3h43m ago)	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-persistenceagent-6f86458589-9nsdh	1/1	Running	3 (3h46m ago)	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-scheduledworkflow-6d47f64655-mht2c	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-ui-59864db569-m7xrf	1/1	Running	1 (3h50m ago)	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-viewer-crd-c84f488f8-qh7gw	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	ml-pipeline-visualizationserver-b688864fb-8nwd9	1/1	Running	0	3h59m
kubeflow	mysql-5f8cbd6df7-9nmt	1/1	Running	0	3h59m

Figure 4 Pods showing the correct installation of Kubeflow Pipelines.

Once Kubeflow is deployed, access the Kubeflow dashboard. This can typically be done via a web interface provided by your Kubernetes cluster. For instance, with Minikube, you can use:

```
minikube service kubeflow-dashboard
```

Or, if preferring to do it via web interface:

```
kubectll port-forward -n kubeflow svc/ml-pipeline-ui 8080:80
```

E3.6.2: Final design for distributed AI operations in 6G

Figure 5 Kubeflow Pipelines User Interface.

After the pipelines have been designed in Python, we can observe the pipelines using the UI of the dashboard:

Figure 6 Pipelines deployed in the UI.

10 Conclusion

To sum up, the integration of AI into network operations is essential for the future-proofing of 6G networks. The final design of distributed MLOps architecture offers a modular, scalable solution by consolidating MLOps into a dedicated plane, enhancing model reusability, reducing training workloads. This deliverable highlights the critical components of this architecture, including i2CAT statistical data aggregation and model trustworthiness verification, as well as the use of Kubeflow for efficient MLOps implementation in a cloud-edge continuum. Interconnection with OPTARE Feature store (FEAST) and OpenNebula AIOps and edge orchestrator is also detailed.